

THE CONCEPT OF CLASSIFICATION OF CRIMES

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The issue of classification of crimes has been attracting the attention of representatives of the legal field for many years, in particular, legal scholars, experts, and law enforcement agencies. The reason is that by classifying crimes, it is possible to assign a suitable punishment to a committed socially dangerous crime and thereby achieve the purpose of the punishment.

In fact, when studying a particular field, systematization works well. With systematization, the object can be learned not only quickly and easily, but also improved.

Classification is derived from Latin (clasis-level, fasio-do) is the classification of objects, events and concepts according to their general characteristics by class, section, level.

Classification is the first and most important step a researcher must take for any large and diverse group of phenomena. Classification as a method of study has two meanings for a scientific researcher: from the outside, it is a method that introduces system and order to the research, and from the inside, it is a method that predetermines the completeness and diversity of the research results.

Classification is one of the methods of knowing the phenomena of nature and society, as well as a method of solving problems in one or another practical activity of a person. Systematization of the studied objects, dividing them into parts and groups, should be carried out without losing their interdependence. If the whole is divided into parts, then the whole can be understood from the parts, or vice versa. It is possible to study the object in depth with this kind of study. In any classification, the principle of reciprocity between the selected objects is of great importance. This principle suggests that the main characteristics of the object should be clearly distinguished, and its interaction with other objects should be analyzed and synthesized.

As L. N. Krivochenko said, the main task of classification is to reflect typical objective signs, based on which it is possible to group the classified objects and determine their place in the set.

But in classification, first of all, it is necessary to emphasize the function of dividing all sets of objects to be classified into groups based on the selected criteria for similarities and differences.

The criterion is the theoretical and practical significance of the entire classification, the indicator of the goals and tasks assigned to it. On the other hand, the nature of the selected criterion mainly shows the knowledge of the person about the classified phenomena, the depth of access to its essence. Therefore, when choosing classification criteria, it is necessary to keep in mind the purpose of such classification, whether there are any practical needs for it. The concept of classification is used in all fields, and the field of law is no exception. M.Usmonaliev approached this issue from a different perspective and defined the division of crimes into categories based on one or another characteristic as the classification of crimes.

Classification in criminal law is considered a unique method of legal technique, it is used to divide legal norms into specific categories (groups, types) according to a single criterion, and for the purpose of uniform understanding and use of criminal legal institutions and norms.

According to S.S. Alekseev, classification is systematization, systematization - regulation of current laws, normative documents, legal norms. Undoubtedly, legislation needs constant regulation. Because only systematized and established laws can be understood and accepted by citizens.

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is such a systematic legal document. A natural classification method was used to systematize it. First of all, this Code is divided into two parts: General and Special.

The General part of the Criminal Code consists of the general rules and principles of criminal law, and is related to two main concepts, which are the concepts of crime and punishment. The functions and principles of the Criminal Code, the scope and time of the criminal law, the basis of criminal responsibility, guilt and its forms, the age of criminal responsibility and the range of persons who can be held responsible, the circumstances that exclude the criminality of the crime, the purpose of punishment and any determines the system of criminal punishment, criminal responsibility and punishment, exemption from responsibility or punishment, responsibility of minors and coercive measures in the medical field.

The Special Part of the Criminal Code defines certain crimes and punishments for committing these crimes. Although the criminal law consists of two parts, these parts do not have independent branches of law, but they form a single criminal law that is closely related to each other. Their unity lies in the unity of their tasks and in the fact that one cannot exist without the other.

There are a number of classification methods. Including:

- The articles of the Special part of the Criminal Code are classified according to the nature and degree of social danger (social risk is not high, not very serious, serious, very serious).

During the years of independence in our country, significant work was done to build a strong democratic state and civil society. Today's reforms require fundamental changes not only in politics and economy, but also in the field of reforming the legal system. The deepening of these democratic reforms serves to form a strong civil society, as well as to ensure the protection of human rights and freedoms, to increase the well-being of the population, to solve the vital problems and needs of citizens, to ensure the rule of law, legality and justice in society.

At present, one of the general directions of the state's criminal policy at the stage of development is the differentiation and individualization of criminal responsibility carried out by the lawmaker. Classification of crimes is one of the important means of distinguishing responsibility in criminal law documents.

It should be said that regardless of a number of criminal-legal reforms carried out within the framework of the criminal law, the model of classification of crimes has remained unchanged.

At this point, the system and criteria for the classification of crimes by introducing alternative indicators that determine the level and nature of social danger of criminal activity in the "Concept of Improving the Criminal and Criminal Procedural Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan" approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PK-3723 of May 14, 2018 It is necessary to change the model of classification of crimes.

The current trends in the criminal-legal policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan require a review of the issues of classification of crimes, their system and criteria, introduction of new forms

and criteria of classification into the Criminal Code, a deep analysis of the experiences of foreign countries in this framework.

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